

A Study of Students' Adjustment in Relation to Maternal Employment

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In our Indian society, the upbringing of children involves various factors where the profession of parents and the structure of families are equally important. This research paper studied the status of adjustment among children in such families, and explored how these aspects affect students' academic, social, and emotional adjustment in a population of 200 students (aged 14-18) from the schools in the city of Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh. Comparative study of adjustments in students from families with working versus non-working mothers, joint versus nuclear families, and the gender of the children was our primary concern in understanding how family environment and maternal employment status impact student adjustment and their social development. Data collections were done through the tool Adjustment Inventory of School Students AISS by Sinha and Singh (1971). A random sampling and the ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) method were used to compare the adjustment levels between different groups. Results of this study underscore the significance of strong family support and parental involvement in facilitating students' successful adjustment and adaptation. Finally, the study concludes that students from nuclear families and those with working mothers may benefit from targeted interventions. Research insights can help educators, parents, and policymakers develop strategies to improve student well-being and performance across diverse family backgrounds.

Keywords: Family structure, maternal employment, nuclear families, joint families, social and emotional adjustment

Increasing participation of women in the nation's workforce has drawn academic attention to the interplay between maternal employment and child development, particularly in psychosocial and academic adjustment. In the 21st century, maternal employment is no longer a fringe phenomenon but a central element of family dynamics, demanding critical analysis of its multifaceted impact on children and adolescents.

An adjustment refers to a child's ability to adapt effectively to the academic, social, and emotional demands of school life. This covers how students cope with challenges, regulate emotions, interact with peers and teachers, and perform academically. An adjustment is a multidimensional construct, including academic adjustment (performance, motivation, homework management), social adjustment (peer relationships, cooperation, conflict resolution), and emotional adjustment (self-concept, anxiety management, emotion regulation) (Baker & Siryk, 1989; Huebner, 2004).

Academic Adjustment

An academic adjustment refers to a student's ability to manage learning tasks, maintain motivation, and meet school expectations. Some studies have shown that students with positive academic

adjustment demonstrate higher achievement, better time management, and persistence in challenging tasks (Roeser, Eccles, & Sameroff, 2000). Mother's employment can indirectly influence academic adjustment through parenting quality, supervision of homework, and availability of learning resources (Buehler & O'Brien, 2011).

About Social Adjustment

Social adjustment pertains to how children navigate interpersonal relationships within school. It includes building friendships, resolving conflicts, and exhibiting prosocial behaviours. Studies indicate that children who experience supportive family environments, consistent parental involvement, and secure attachments are better able to form positive peer relationships and handle social challenges (Sroufe et al., 2005; Hill & Tyson, 2009).

An Emotional Adjustment

Emotional adjustment refers to the child's capacity to regulate feelings such as anxiety, anger, or sadness, and to maintain a positive self-concept. Children with healthy emotional adjustment can cope with stress, recover from setbacks, and engage productively in learning activities. Secure attachment with parents, quality mother-child interactions, and supportive family systems enhance emotional adjustment, while a lack of parental engagement or high-stress environments can increase vulnerability to anxiety, depression, and behavioural issues (Bowlby, 1988; Lazarus, 1991).

Factors Influencing Student Adjustment

A number of factors contribute to how well a student adjusts, including family structure, parental employment, socioeconomic status, and gender norms. Example: the children from nuclear families may experience more focused parental attention but less extended family support, affecting adjustment in complex ways

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(Tiwari et al., 2024). Factors of gender-related expectations also influence emotional and social adjustment, with studies showing differences in peer interactions and self-perception between boys and girls (Tonei, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

Study is guided by three major perspectives: Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979), Lazarus's Cognitive Appraisal Theory (1991), and Bowlby's Attachment Theory (1988). These frameworks provide a comprehensive lens to understand how maternal employment influences children's academic, social, and emotional adjustment by examining both environmental systems and the child's cognitive-emotional processes.

From an ecological perspective, children's adjustment is embedded within multiple, interacting layers of influence. The macrosystem level, broader cultural and societal attitudes toward maternal employment, gender role expectations, and institutional supports such as maternity leave, workplace flexibility, and childcare policies (Ray et al., 2010) create the backdrop against which children's experiences unfold. The exosystem, particularly the mother's workplace environment, also plays a crucial role. Factors such as work hours, stress levels, and job satisfaction can influence parenting practices, with supportive work conditions often linked to warm and consistent parenting (Buehler & O'Brien, 2011). Similarly, the availability of reliable childcare can ease work-family conflict and promote positive child outcomes (Laughlin, 2013).

Mesosystem reflects the home-school connection, where maternal employment may shape the extent of parental involvement in school activities and the quality of mother-teacher interactions—both of which affect children's academic and social adjustment (Hill & Tyson, 2009). The level of microsystem, children are directly influenced by everyday interactions within the home, including the warmth and responsiveness of mother-child relationships, the presence of alternative caregivers, and the parenting style adopted. Research suggests that parenting approaches significantly mediate both academic and emotional outcomes (Baumrind, 1991).

Beyond environmental influences, the cognitive-affective domain highlights the child's inner world. Attachment security fosters emotional regulation, resilience, and positive coping (Sroufe et al., 2005). Children's interpretations of maternal employment—whether perceived as abandonment or empowerment—further shape their self-concept and adjustment, consistent with Cognitive Appraisal Theory. Secure early bonds also underpin the development of self-regulation and adaptive coping strategies.

Ultimately, the adjustment outcomes influenced by maternal employment span three areas: academic (e.g., performance, motivation, homework completion), social (e.g., peer relations, conflict resolution, prosocial behavior), and emotional (e.g., self-concept, anxiety, emotion regulation). Importantly, the impact of maternal employment is not uniform but depends on the quality of mother-child interactions, the balance mothers achieve between work and home roles, the support systems available, and individual child temperament (Voydanoff, 2005).

Review of Literature

Recent research indicates that maternal employment can exert both beneficial and adverse influences on student adjustment, depending on variables such as work schedule flexibility, socioeconomic status,

and the presence of support systems. For example, Kisanga and Matiba (2023) found that maternal employment often necessitates the development of adaptive coping mechanisms in student-mothers, such as enhanced time management and emotional regulation, which may model resilience for their children. Conversely, the structure and demands of maternal employment may interfere with parental availability, potentially affecting students' academic focus, emotional stability, or social integration (Lin, 2003).

Maternal employment in India reflects the intersection of tradition, socioeconomic necessity, and evolving policies. While female workforce participation is rising, much of it is in informal sectors with limited protections.

Opportunities: Greater autonomy, improved healthcare utilization, enhanced socioeconomic positioning (Yadav et al., 2021).

Challenges: Inequalities across caste, class, and rural-urban divides; inadequate maternity benefits and childcare (Gupta & Guha, 2018; Mishra et al., 2021).

Evidence: With consistent emotional support, maternal employment does not harm adjustment and may enhance academic perseverance, resilience, and social-emotional development (Raval et al., 2018; Trevethan et al., 2021; Vijayalakshmi & Sequeira, 2017; Shahzad & Saeed, 2023).

Family Dynamics and Student Adjustment Family cohesion, expressiveness, and conflict significantly influence socio-emotional and educational adjustment (Deepshikha & Bhanot, 2011). Joint families provide broader caregiving networks, while nuclear families encourage independence but require stronger self-regulation skills (Chaudhary, 2018; Stewart, 2007). Gender differences and educational settings further shape adjustment outcomes (Manju, 2011; Chauhan, 2013).

This study acknowledges that the COVID-19 pandemic highlights significant shifts in children's academic, social, and emotional adjustment, particularly across different family structures. In nuclear families, children often demonstrated improved adjustment in the post-pandemic phase compared to earlier periods. Increased time spent with parents during lockdowns strengthened parent-child bonding, facilitated secure attachment, and provided opportunities for open communication. Such experiences contributed to greater emotional security and resilience in children (Singh & Mishra, 2022).

Maternal employment can provide financial stability and serve as a positive role model, yet it may reduce direct parental involvement (Sharma & Saini, 2013; Bianchi, 2000). Family systems and attachment theories suggest that emotional bonds and parental consistency play a key role in fostering better adjustment (Amato & Keith, 1991; Bowen, 1978; Bowlby, 1969). Gender socialization can influence emotional and academic outcomes, with boys often encouraged to express emotions through action and achievement (Maccoby, 2002; Chapman et al., 2003).

Role-modelling has also been identified as a key mediating factor. Children of employed mothers often develop more progressive gender-role attitudes and enhanced adaptability. Weer et al. (2006) demonstrated that college students whose mothers adopted role-altering employment strategies were better prepared to manage future work-family conflicts, highlighting long-term social-emotional adjustment effects.

While previous research often emphasizes risks associated with

maternal employment, particularly in lower-income contexts, there is growing recognition that employment can serve as a protective factor, improving maternal well-being and financial stability, which indirectly promotes healthier developmental environments (Kisanga & Matiba, 2023). Despite decades of inquiry, inconsistencies in findings persist, underscoring the need for renewed empirical attention using nuanced, context-sensitive frameworks.

Gaps in Existing Research

Limited studies focus on the combination of family structure (nuclear vs. joint), maternal employment, and gender influence on children's educational, social, and emotional adjustment.

The moderating role of parental involvement and support systems remains underexplored in semi-urban contexts.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The present study aims to explore the effects of maternal employment on their children's educational, social, and emotional adjustment. It also looks into how family structure (nuclear vs. joint) and gender affect children's performance. This research will try to update the existing gap related to less explored research study of working women's family complications and their children's rising issues in a semi-urban context. The results of this study may help in understanding women's psychological state and support in minimizing their overall health complications.

Hypothesis of the Study

This study hypothesizes that there may be a significant difference between the children of working and non-working mothers in the context of their adjustment to educational, emotional, and social aspects. The study also assumes that family structure and gender differences will significantly influence the students' adjustment criteria.

Method

Participants

The present study targets the population of school students from a semi-urban area belonging to the district of Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India. About 200 students were approached from different schools in the same city, and 160 students responded from the desired research demography settings.

Students were selected through random sampling from working mother families and non-working mother families. $N=160$, working mothers (total no. of students=80), and non-working mothers (total no. of students=80). We have gathered a sample of students from different family backgrounds, aiming to reflect a variety of family dynamics. In addition, we are also looking forward to gender influence. Working mothers, the students are split across two family structures: The Nuclear families consist of both boys and girls, with 20 students from each gender. The Joint families also feature boys and girls, with 20 students from each group. Non-working mothers, the design mirrors the working mothers' structure, again considering both family settings: The nuclear families, there are 20 boys and 20 girls, providing a balanced representation. In the joint families, the same gender distribution holds, with 20 boys and 20 girls. In approach allows us to closely examine the unique experiences and challenges faced by students from various family structures, whether their mothers are working or not, and how gender might play a role in

these experiences.

Independent Variables

Maternal Employment, Family Structure, and Gender.

Dependent Variables

Educational Adjustment, Social Adjustment, and Emotional Adjustment.

Measure

Adjustment Inventory for School Students by Sinha and Singh (1971). "This inventory is designed to assess the adjustment levels of secondary school students across three key dimensions: emotional, social, and educational. Inventory has a total of 60 items, with 20 items to evaluate each specific area (educational, emotional, & social adjustment). This questionnaire aims to understand how students navigate their emotional experiences, social relationships, and educational environments."

Procedure

Before gathering data, the school authorities granted the necessary permissions, and consent was secured from both the students and their parents/ guardians. The students were guaranteed that their responses would remain confidential and anonymous.

Data Collection

Attendants for this test were briefed about the purpose of the study and given brief instructions on how to respond to the questionnaires. Inventories were administered in a classroom setting under the guidance of the researcher. The average time to complete the questionnaires was approximately 3040 minutes.

Data Screening

Collected data were checked for completeness and consistency, and incomplete or ambiguous responses were excluded from the analysis.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The following statistical techniques were employed: Descriptive Statistics Mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage were used to describe the sample characteristics and adjustment levels. ONE-WAY ANOVA Used to compare the adjustment levels between different groups (e.g., nuclear vs. joint families, working vs. non-working mothers, boys vs. Girls).

Results

The results revealed that students with working mothers reported significantly higher adjustment levels across all domains: educational, emotional, and social adjustment. Similarly, students from nuclear families showed significantly better adjustment than those from joint families. Gender comparisons showed that boys had significantly higher adjustment than girls in all three areas: educational, emotional, and social. Results have shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3 that these outcomes support the alternate hypotheses that maternal employment, family structure, and gender significantly influence students' educational, social, and emotional adjustment. Figures 1, 2, and 3 present the comparison between different groups.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics and ONE-WAY ANOVA for Educational, Emotional, and Social Adjustment by Maternal Employment Status

Variable	Group	M	SD	SE	df	F	p
Educational Adjustment	Working Mother	22.05	12.08	1.35	1	51.05	< .001
	Non-Working Mother	9.50	10.05	1.12	1		
Emotional Adjustment	Working Mother	22.10	12.01	1.34	1	51.80	< .001
	Non-Working Mother	9.50	10.05	1.12	1		
Social Adjustment	Working Mother	22.15	11.96	1.34	1	52.47	< .001
	Non-Working Mother	9.50	10.05	1.12	1		

Note. *M* = Mean; *SD* = Standard Deviation; *SE* = Standard Error; *df* = degrees of freedom; *F* = F ratio; *p* = significance level

Figure 1

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics and ONE-WAY ANOVA for Educational, Emotional, and Social Adjustment by Family Type

Variable	Group	M	SD	SE	df	F	p
Educational Adjustment	Nuclear Family	21.00	13.08	1.46	1	32.20	< .001
	Joint Family	10.55	10.01	1.12	1		
Emotional Adjustment	Nuclear Family	21.00	13.08	1.46	1	31.95	< .001
	Joint Family	10.60	9.98	1.12	1		
Social Adjustment	Nuclear Family	21.00	13.08	1.46	1	31.65	< .001
	Joint Family	10.65	9.98	1.12	1		

Note. *M* = Mean; *SD* = Standard Deviation; *SE* = Standard Error; *df* = degrees of freedom; *F* = F ratio; *p* = significance level

Figure 2

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics and ONE-WAY ANOVA for Educational, Emotional, and Social Adjustment by Gender

Variable	Group	M	SD	SE	df	F	p
Educational Adjustment	Girl	9.50	10.05	1.12	1	32.20	< .001
	Boy	22.05	12.08	1.35			
Emotional Adjustment	Girl	9.50	10.05	1.12	1	31.95	< .001
	Boy	22.10	12.01	1.34			
Social Adjustment	Girl	9.50	10.05	1.12	1	31.65	< .001
	Boy	22.15	11.96	1.34			

Note. *M* = Mean; *SD* = Standard Deviation; *SE* = Standard Error; *df* = degrees of freedom; *F* = F ratio; *p* = significance level

Figure 3

Findings of the Study

Maternal Employment Status

The one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of maternal employment on students' adjustment. The results showed in Table 1, a significant difference between students of working and non-working mothers across all domains. The students of working mothers scored significantly higher on educational adjustment ($M = 22.05, SD = 12.08$) compared to students of non-working mothers ($M = 9.50, SD = 10.05$), $F(1,158) = 51.05, p < .001$. Similarly, emotional adjustment was higher for students of working mothers ($M = 22.10, SD = 12.01$) than non-working mothers ($M = 9.50, SD = 10.05$), $F(1,158) = 51.80, p < .001$. In social adjustment also showed a significant difference, with students of working mothers ($M = 22.15, SD = 11.96$) scoring higher than those of non-working mothers ($M = 9.50, SD = 10.05$), $F(1,158) = 52.47, p < .001$.

Family Type

Our results further revealed significant differences in adjustment based on family structure. Table 2, students from nuclear families reported higher educational adjustment ($M = 21.00, SD = 13.08$) compared to those from joint families ($M = 10.55, SD = 10.01$), $F(1,158) = 32.20, p < .001$. The emotional adjustment was also higher among nuclear family students ($M = 21.00, SD = 13.08$) than joint family students ($M = 10.60, SD = 9.98$), $F(1,158) = 31.95, p < .001$. The third output of the data showed that students from nuclear families ($M = 21.00, SD = 13.08$) had greater social adjustment than those from joint families ($M = 10.65, SD = 9.98$), $F(1,158) = 31.65, p < .001$.

Gender

Our third output was the examination of gender-based differences. In Table 3, the boys showed significantly higher educational adjustment ($M = 22.05, SD = 12.08$) compared to girls ($M = 9.50, SD = 10.05$), $F(1,158) = 51.05, p < .001$. The emotional adjustment was also greater among boys ($M = 22.10, SD = 12.01$) than girls ($M = 9.50, SD = 10.05$), $F(1,158) = 51.80, p < .001$. In this way, boys reported higher social adjustment ($M = 22.15, SD = 11.96$) compared to girls ($M = 9.50, SD = 10.05$), $F(1,158) = 52.47, p < .001$.

Discussion

Study outcomes indicated that children of working mothers demonstrated significantly higher educational, emotional, and social adjustment compared to those of non-working mothers. However, some traditional perspectives suggest that maternal employment may reduce the time available for childcare; recent evidence shows otherwise (Hoffman & Youngblade, 1999). Argued that working mothers often provide children with more structured routines, independence, and role models of achievement. In addition, employed mothers may compensate for their time constraints by engaging in higher-quality interactions, leading to better psychosocial outcomes (Greenberger & O'Neil, 1993). Perhaps the study explains why, in the present study, children of working mothers showed superior adjustment across all domains.

Our study also revealed that students from nuclear families reported higher adjustment than those from joint families. Study outcome may be linked to the fact that nuclear families often allow parents to devote more individualized attention and resources to

their children (Singh & Kiran, 2014). Found that nuclear families foster autonomy and emotional closeness, which can enhance students' academic and social outcomes. However, while joint families provide extended social networks, they can also be associated with intergenerational conflicts, inconsistent parenting, and divided attention, which may hinder children's adjustment (Sharma & Sharma, 2018).

A gender differences were also observed, with boys demonstrating higher educational, emotional, and social adjustment than girls. Some studies suggest girls are more emotionally resilient, research in certain cultural contexts supports the present finding. As an example, Rani and Singh (2016) noted that boys often receive greater parental and societal encouragement for academic and social pursuits, which strengthens their adjustment. Other hand, girls may face restrictions, additional household responsibilities, or differential treatment, leading to relatively lower adjustment outcomes (Verma & Saraswat, 2017).

Results highlight the dynamic influence of family structure, maternal employment, and gender on child development. They align with Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological systems theory, which emphasizes the interaction between family, societal roles, and cultural expectations in shaping children's overall adjustment.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that students of working mothers, children from nuclear families, and boys exhibited significantly better educational, emotional, and social adjustment. Research findings, while differing from some traditional expectations, reflect changing family dynamics, gender roles, and parenting patterns in contemporary society. The schools and parents must recognize the positive role of maternal employment, supportive nuclear family environments, and gender-sensitive approaches in promoting student adjustment. Future research should investigate moderating factors such as socio-economic status, parental education, and cultural variations to build a more nuanced understanding of students' adjustment processes.

Statements and Declarations: The following submission has not been previously published, nor is it before another journal for consideration. Since it is part of my PhD work, its publication will add to my eligibility for the award of a PhD degree.

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